

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D1.1 – Quality Management Plan

WP1 – Manage & Coordinate

26/05/2023

Funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Grant Agreement Number	101081179	Acronym	DIAMOND
Full Title	Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development		
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02		
Funding scheme	HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Date	December 2022	Duration	48 Months
Project URL	http://www.climate-diamond.eu/		
EU Project Advisor	Silvia Vaghi		
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems - ICCS		
Deliverable	D1.1 – Quality Management Plan		
Work Package	WP1 – Manage & Coordinate		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/05/2023	Actual 26/05/2023
Nature	Report	Dissemination	Public
Lead Beneficiary	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems		
Responsible Author	Konstantinos Koasidis	Email	kkoasidis@epu.ntua.gr
	ICCS	Phone	+30 210 772 3612
Contributors	Alexandros Nikas, Natasha Frinlingou (ICCS)		
Reviewer(s)	Glen Peters (CICERO); Steve Pye (UCL)		
Keywords	Quality management; project management; quality processes; risk management		

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document among consortium partners (experts and non-experts), to be aware of and kept up to date with the DIAMOND project's quality management procedures, responsibilities, and requirements. It may also be used by individuals outside the consortium, including policymakers and scientists, as a documentation of the quality management plan and the rigorous procedures underpinning the legitimacy of the scientific processes carried out in the project and the results and policy recommendations.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The Quality Management Plan defines the quality policy and plan to be applied in the DIAMOND project. Its purpose is to establish the roles, procedures, metrics, and tools necessary to ensure that the DIAMOND project is implemented smoothly and that all project deliverables are of a high quality and of scientific value and that they are submitted to the EC services in time. Complying with the quality management procedures falls under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager, the Quality Manager, the Work Package leaders, and the Task leaders.

Effective channels of internal communication have been established since Month 1, enabling smooth exchange of all necessary information among project partners.

A thorough quality procedure has been established: each project deliverable will be quality-reviewed by two to five internal reviewers (depending on the nature of the deliverable), before being revised accordingly and then reviewed and edited for a final time by an additional member of the management team from ICCS. This will ensure that the submitted deliverables adequately satisfy the quality criteria of clarity, completeness, accuracy, relevance, and technical compliance.

Specific performance indicators have been set for which monitoring data will be collected regularly, aimed at fully informed reporting. Finally, a risk management plan has been put into place, consisting of the identification of the technical (research-oriented) and management (project implementation-related) risks.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

The “Quality Management Plan” defines the quality policy and plan to be applied in the DIAMOND project. Its purpose is to establish the roles, procedures, metrics, and tools necessary to ensure that the DIAMOND project is implemented smoothly and that all project deliverables are of high quality and of scientific added value and are submitted to the EC services in time. Complying with the quality management procedures falls under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator, the Work Package leaders, and the Tasks leaders.

The DIAMOND Project Coordinator (PC) oversees the scientific and technical direction of the project and the quality of the project deliverables, as well as the financial aspects. The PC is supported by a Project Manager (PM), as well as a project management team from ICCS. In parallel, the Quality Manager (QM) oversees the process and monitors the project progress. Each Work Package (WP) is coordinated by a WP Leader (WPL), responsible for the implementation of the respective WP, in line with the work description. The WPL is responsible for reviewing and evaluating intermediate and final WP outputs in conjunction with other WP partners. The Task Leaders (TLs) are responsible to lead the execution of activities under the respective task and guide the rest of the partners in fulfilling their activities in a timely manner. Furthermore, the General Assembly (GA) is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium, consisting of one representative per partner and the PC, and deciding on aspects related to content, finances, and intellectual property rights, consortium evolution, and member appointments. The Executive Board (EB) is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report—and be accountable—to the GA, consisting of the PC and the representatives of all Parties, as appointed by the GA, and monitoring the effective and efficient implementation of the project. The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) comprises external international experts recognised in the climate and policy area, whose role is to advise the consortium on matters related to the implementation and development of the project activities.

The PC is also responsible for the preparation of template documents for the various project outputs and management reports; the establishment of a document management system; and the assurance of compliance with the document naming conventions, in the aim of securing the high quality of project implementation. Effective channels of internal communication have been established since Month 1, for smooth exchange of necessary information among the partners. The means for conveying information range from physical meetings and teleconferencing facilities to an internal workspace for document management and weekly structured e-mail communication, allowing partners to have full overview of the project progress and requirements.

Quality control takes place via monthly calls and meeting between the QM (CICERO), the PC (ICCS), and the WPLs to discuss work progress through detailed reports on the progress for each task. Emphasis is laid on quality assurance of deliverables, which is planned to be achieved with the coordinated input from the project partners, each of whom undertake clear roles in the review process. A thorough quality procedure shall be followed; each project deliverable will be quality-reviewed by two to five internal reviewers (members of the consortium partners), before being finally reviewed by the PM and edited by an additional member of the management team from ICCS, ensuring that the submitted deliverables adequately satisfy the quality criteria of clarity, completeness, accuracy, relevance, and technical compliance.

Specific performance indicators have been set since the proposal phase and monitoring data will be collected regularly, aimed at fully informed reporting and at allowing for proper self-assessment of results. Finally, a risk management plan is put into place, consisting of the identification of the technical (research-oriented) and management (project implementation-related) risks; the assessment of their degree of occurrence, and of their potential impact; and of reducing the possibility of materialisation for each one of the risks already foreseen in the design of the project by planning the necessary mitigation measures to be taken during implementation.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Purpose and Scope.....	1
1.2	Structure of the document.....	1
2	Project Management ensuring quality.....	2
2.1	Project Governance	2
2.2	Project management actors, roles, and responsibilities	2
2.3	Project management structure.....	4
2.4	Project management processes	5
2.4.1	Document Management.....	5
2.4.2	Document management system.....	8
2.5	Internal communication.....	10
2.5.1	Physical meetings	10
2.5.2	Remote meetings.....	11
2.5.3	Weekly updates	11
2.6	Internal reporting	11
2.7	Official reporting	12
2.8	Quality Assurance of Deliverables	13
2.8.1	Review roles and responsibilities.....	13
2.8.2	Deliverable Review process.....	14
2.9	Quality Assurance of other material	16
3	Quality assessment.....	17
3.1	Evaluation framework.....	17
3.2	Performance indicators.....	17
4	Risk management plan	18
4.1	Risk analysis and mitigation measures	18
	ANNEX I: Allocation of reviewers to deliverables (Year 1)	21
	ANNEX II: Outcome & Impact Indicators	22
	ANNEX III: Communication and Dissemination activities and indicators	25
	ANNEX IV: Quality indicators	27

Table of Figures

Figure 1.	The DIAMOND management structure	5
Figure 2.	The DIAMOND internal data management platform	9

Table of Tables

Table 1. Work Package Leaders in DIAMOND	3
Table 2. Documents to be produced in DIAMOND	5
Table 3. Naming convention for the DIAMOND Deliverables	7
Table 4. Naming convention for the DIAMOND reviewed Deliverables	7
Table 5. Naming convention for documents related to DIAMOND meetings and events	8
Table 6. Naming conventions for official reports submitted to the EC	8
Table 7. Naming conventions for internal documents which are regularly updated	8
Table 8. Naming convention for DIAMOND materials/publications	8
Table 9. SharePoint functionalities securing proper document management.	9
Table 10. Tentative schedule of DIAMOND physical (GA) meetings.	10
Table 11. Process for the delivery of the official progress reports	12
Table 12. Deliverable Review process.....	14
Table 13. Quality criteria for deliverables.....	15
Table 14. Linguistic values for risk impact and risk probability occurrence	18
Table 15. Identified risks and mitigation measures	19

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of the Quality Management Plan (QMP) is to establish the roles, procedures, metrics, and tools necessary to ensure that the DIAMOND project is implemented smoothly and that all project deliverables are of high quality and scientific value and submitted to the EC services on time.

In this context, the objectives of this deliverable (D1.1) are to:

- define clear project management roles and responsibilities of all partners within the consortium;
- establish the processes for ensuring the quality and timely execution of project deliverables and milestones, and the project management activities;
- present the coordination and communication channels and processes among partners, during the project lifetime, which will secure smooth information flow;
- analyse the potential risks of the project and evaluate their impact and exposure; and
- proactively define risk mitigation measures to guarantee seamless and proper execution of the project's tasks.

Moreover, to ensure its relevance throughout the lifetime of the project, the QMP will be revisited regularly and updated when deemed necessary. All DIAMOND partners, European and international, are obliged to comply with the requirements set out in this document.

1.2 Structure of the document

The structure of this document is as follows:

- Section 2 provides an overview of the project governance, management structure and responsibilities, including the responsibilities for quality assurance. Moreover, this section presents the processes for internal communication, reporting and quality assurance of the deliverables and other materials/outputs, as well as the tools for effective document management.
- Section 3 presents the quality assessment framework, including the performance indicators aimed at continuous improvement throughout the project lifetime.
- Section 4 analyses the risks that may jeopardise quality and sets out the planned mitigation measures.
- Annex I: Allocation of reviewers to deliverables (Year 1)
- Annex II: Outcome & Impact indicators
- Annex III: Communication and Dissemination indicators
- Annex IV: Quality indicators

2 Project Management ensuring quality

The DIAMOND governance and management structure guarantees smooth decision-making, prompt management of risks and unforeseen events, suitable interaction with relevant stakeholders, and direct participation of all partners in the operations of the project.

2.1 Project Governance

The **General Assembly (GA)** is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. The GA consists of one representative from each partner and the Project Coordinator (PC) from ICCS. The PC chairs all meetings of the GA, unless decided otherwise by the GA.

The decisions taken by the GA relate to, among others: (a) content, finances, and intellectual property rights; (b) evolution of the consortium; and (c) member appointments.

The **Executive Board (EB)** is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report—and be accountable—to the GA. The Executive Board consists of the Coordinator and the representatives of the Parties appointed to it by the GA. The PC chairs all meetings of the EB, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds. The EB monitors the effective and efficient implementation of the Project, ensuring that all required procedures are workable, implementable, and clear for all Project Partners. This includes contributing to the development of the Project's quality management plan, outlining quality processes for all Project deliverables.

The activities of the EB include, among others: (a) preparing the meetings, proposing decisions, and preparing the agenda of the GA; (b) proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GA; (c) seeking a consensus among the Parties; (d) management and monitoring of project development according to the work plan; (e) supporting the PC in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables; and (f) preparing the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority.

The operational procedures for the EB and the decisions to be made by the GA are fully described in Section 6.3 of the DIAMOND Consortium Agreement.

2.2 Project management actors, roles, and responsibilities

The DIAMOND **Project Coordinator (PC)**, Prof. Haris Doukas (ICCS-NTUA), oversees the scientific and technical direction of the project and the project deliverables, manages financial planning and control, and communicates with the EC's Project Advisor (PA).

The PC is responsible for:

- monitoring all partners' compliance with their obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement;
- keeping the address list of members of all DIAMOND partners and other contact persons updated and available;
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency, and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority;
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of the GA meetings, chairing the meetings (unless otherwise decided by the GA, in which case a different chairperson is selected), preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions made at meetings;
- transmitting documents and information connected with the project to any Party concerned;
- administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2 of the DIAMOND Consortium Agreement.

An exhaustive list of all responsibilities of the PC are presented in detail in the DIAMOND Consortium Agreement, to which all partners have agreed and will adhere.

Linked with the present deliverable, the PC has the responsibility of ensuring that the quality management procedures (described in the following Sections) are respected by all DIAMOND partners.

The PC is supported by a **Project Manager (PM)**, namely Dr. Alexandros Nikas, as well as a project management team from ICCS. They will focus on the day-to-day administration of the project. They will work closely with the PC, providing support with the financial and overall management and communication with all partners. The PM is also involved in setting up and overseeing the internal communication platform (in Task 1.2 in the Grant Agreement). Finally, the PM will have the responsibility for the scientific/research progress and will be referring to the PC in this respect.

The **Quality Manager (QM)**, Dr. Glen Peters from CICERO, will be overseeing the process for the monitoring of the project progress. If there emerge deviations from the project plan, the QM—alongside the PC and the responsible partners—will discuss how the progress can be realigned with the plan. It is noted that the day-to-day monitoring against the quality standards, as described in the present document, will be performed by the management team from ICCS.

Each WP is coordinated by **WP Leaders (WPLs)**, responsible for the implementation of the respective WP in line with the work description. The WPLs are responsible for reviewing and evaluating intermediate and final WP outputs in conjunction with other WP partners; and for cooperating with other WPLs. WPLs are responsible for:

- coordinating the WP tasks with Task Leads (TLs), including technical and management activities;
- ensuring that the WP fulfils the objectives listed as milestones and deliverables;
- monitoring progress against time, budget allocations and the expected outcomes;
- implementing corrective actions if needed;
- delivering required information for the preparation of all plans and reports;
- participating in monthly calls with the PC and QM to discuss work progress;
- preparing the consolidated WP reports on a quarterly basis or otherwise, as required;
- stimulating interaction and proactive sharing of information with other WPs;
- assigning internal reviews of draft deliverables, for content/editing, prior to finalisation and submission

The WPLs have the responsibility for the high quality of the respective technical deliverables and other materials related to their WPs. The WPLs are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Work Package Leaders in DIAMOND

WP No	Leads	Co-leads
WP1	Haris Doukas and Alexandros Nikas (ICCS)	-
WP2	Carlo Sessa and Daniel Cassolà (ISINNOVA)	Bianca V. Baptista, Stephanie Briers (ETH)
WP3	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven (BC3)	Gabriele Cassetti (E4SMA)
WP4	Adam Hawkes and Shivika Mittal (Imperial)	-
WP5	Glen Peters and Ben Sanderson (CICERO)	-
WP6	Konstantinos Koasidis and Alexandros Nikas (ICCS)	Georgios Xexakis (HOLISTIC)
WP7	Georgia Polutanou and Georgios Xexakis (HOLISTIC)	-

The **Task Leaders (TLs)** are responsible to lead the execution of activities under the respective task and guide the rest of the partners in fulfilling their activities in a timely manner. More specifically, the TLs are responsible for:

- planning and monitoring activities outlined in each task;
- developing the respective data exchange templates, where needed, with the contribution of the WPL;
- communicating regularly with the WPL in order to discuss progress;
- communicating potential problems identified during the implementation of the activities;

- compiling partners' input in one integrated deliverable;
- sending the draft deliverable in time to the WPL for comments;
- integrating partners' comments in the deliverable to produce the final version;
- ensuring timely submission of related deliverables..

The **consortium partners/contributors to tasks** are responsible for:

- responding to requests by the TLs, WPLs, and the PC in a timely manner, in line with the set deadlines;
- reporting any difficulties encountered during the implementation of their activities to the TL—when these difficulties affect the timely submission of their contribution or the quality or impact of their work, then mitigation actions should be suggested and decided with the WPL and the PC;
- communicating new risks identified for mitigation measures to be taken to the corresponding TLs, and WPLs as well as the PC; and
- developing deliverables and ensuring that these are of high quality and can be published/submitted to the EC services.

Project partners will comply with all ethical standards deriving from national, European, and international laws. Moreover, the respective research methods will agree to the code of ethical research of the EU, as well as any additional codes referring to their own institution or professional bodies, obtaining ethical approval of the responsible organisations. In addition, the compliance with ethical codes will be ensured by the consortium via ethical review processes.

The envisaged research activities will not require the collection of individual information and the names of participants will not be revealed in the research: all stakeholder input envisaged to drive or co-produce the scientific activities and outputs and respective personal data will be anonymised and therefore does not fall under the data privacy rules. Information from the stakeholder database will be strictly confidential, remain undisclosed in all stages of the research, and only be used for contacting stakeholders.

2.3 Project management structure

The DIAMOND management structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The DIAMOND management structure

The Scientific Advisory Board does not have management mandates as such, but they will be interacting with the management bodies of the project.

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) is composed of external international experts recognised in the climate and policy area. Their role is to advise the Consortium on matters related to the implementation and development of the DIAMOND project activities, including but not limited to the scope, transparency, and legitimacy of the activities and methods applied as well as the robustness, quality and dissemination of the results produced.

2.4 Project management processes

2.4.1 Document Management

2.4.1.1 Documentation Requirements

Document management refers to the preparation of template documents for the various project outputs and management reports; the establishment of a document management system; and the assurance of compliance with the document naming conventions. The above-mentioned tasks are under the responsibility of the PC.

During DIAMOND, fifty (50) deliverables and several types of documents will be produced, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Documents to be produced in DIAMOND

Documents	Responsible	Type	Template
50 Deliverables submitted to the EC	As per Annex I (Part A) of the Grant Agreement	External-output	Deliverable Document Template (i.e., the template used for the present Deliverable)
Internal Project Presentation	Project Coordinator	External-promotion	Project Presentation Template

Meeting/Event Agenda	Partner hosting the Meeting/Event	External-management	Meeting/Event Agenda Template
Meeting Minutes	Partner hosting the Meeting	External-management	Meeting Minutes Template
Internal Effort and Cost Reporting	All partners	Internal-monitoring	Internal Effort and Cost Reporting Template
Periodic Report PART B	Project Coordinator	External-management	As per Grant Agreement and Commission guidelines
Commentaries/Working documents/Model Documentations/Policy briefs	All Partners	External-scientific and policy level	Commentaries Template/Working document Template/Documentation Template/Policy brief Template
Articles in scientific journals (papers), presentations and/or (extended) abstracts or short papers in scientific conferences	All Partners	External-scientific	According to journal guidelines
Datasets & guidelines for validating as well as reproducing papers	Project Coordinator	External-scientific	Zenodo-specific documentation template

These documents should (and will) comply with the following standards:

- Word Processor: Microsoft Word 2013 or higher,
- Spreadsheet: Microsoft Excel 2013 or higher,
- Presentations: Microsoft PowerPoint 2013 or higher.

In case partners cannot comply with above standards due to limited capacity, ICCS will ensure that the documents are converted as per standards.

2.4.1.2 Naming conventions and versioning

Document configuration management will be ensured by tracking the history of changes within the following project documents:

- Deliverables
- Project/WP Meetings agendas and minutes
- Project events agendas
- Official reports to the EC
- Documents, such as mailing lists and internal effort reporting, which are regularly updated
- Documents used for internal project management and monitoring purposes
- Materials/Publications produced by the project, such as commentaries, policy briefs, working documents, presentations, newsletters

Document history is tracked in each deliverable through a dedicated functionality offered by SharePoint. Tables 3 and 4 show the naming conventions for the draft deliverable ready for internal review, and the revised deliverable after the internal review.

The naming conventions of the final deliverables to be submitted should follow the guidelines established under

D6.1 “Open Data Management Plan”, rendering the reports machine actionable.

Table 3. Naming convention for the DIAMOND Deliverables

Name	DIAMOND DX.Y [Deliverable title]-vA.BB
where	X: Work Package number
	Y: Deliverable number
	A: Major version of the deliverable
	BB: Minor version of the deliverable for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.01
	DIAMOND_D1.1_Quality_Management_Plan: this format should be used for the submitted document to the EC. For record purposes a “-v1.00” disclaimer can be used to indicate the version initially submitted to the EC
Notes	If the Deliverable title is longer than 50 characters (with spaces) then the title should be shortened accordingly by the Deliverable leader.

Table 4. Naming convention for the DIAMOND reviewed Deliverables

Name	DIAMOND DX.Y [Deliverable title]-vA.BB_IN
where	X: Work Package number
	Y: Deliverable number
	A: Major version of the deliverable
	BB: Minor version of the deliverable for updates during preparation phase
	IN: Initials of the reviewer’s name
Examples	DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.08_HD
	DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan -v0.12_SP

For example, the people involved in this deliverable D1.1 Quality Management Plan are: KK, author responsible; AN, NF: contributing partners; GP, Reviewer 1; SP, Reviewer 2; GP, Quality Manager; and AN, AK, editor (for the roles in the internal review process, see the “Roles and responsibilities” section).

The various names and versions of the deliverable may be:

- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.01 (this version is typically the one to include only the Table of Contents, to be further edited by the contributing partners)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.08 (first draft of the deliverable submitted to the PM for internal review)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan_AN (first draft document reviewed by AN and communicated, via the PM, to the Deliverable leader, featuring comments and tracked changes)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.12 (revised deliverable by the Deliverable Leader, having integrated the comments of all reviewers on version 0.08, submitted for further review)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.12_SP (second draft document reviewed by SP and communicated, via the PM, to the Deliverable leader, featuring comments and tracked changes)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.14 (revised deliverable by the Deliverable Leader, after integrating comments of all reviewers on version 0.12)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.14_AK (document modified by contributor AK, based on comments addressed from their side)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v0.17 (final version submitted by the Deliverable Leader to the PM for final review)
- DIAMOND_D1.1_Quality_Management_Plan (final machine actionable version, checked by AN and submitted to the EC)
- DIAMOND D1.1 Quality Management Plan-v1.00 (final version kept for version recording)

Table 5 shows the naming conventions for the various documents related to meetings and events.

Table 5. Naming convention for documents related to DIAMOND meetings and events

Name	DIAMOND DX.Y [Deliverable title]-vA.BB
where	A: Major version of the meeting/event related document
	BB: Minor version of the meeting/event related document for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	DIAMOND KOM Logistics-v0.10
	DIAMOND KOM List of participants-v0.10
	DIAMOND KOM Minutes-v0.10
	DIAMOND Consortium meeting 15th May 2023 Minutes-v1.00
	DIAMOND EB meeting 17th January 2023 Minutes-v1.00
	DIAMOND WP4 meeting 10th December 2022 Minutes-v1.00

Table 6 shows the naming conventions for the official reports to the EC services.

Table 6. Naming conventions for official reports submitted to the EC

Name	DIAMOND DX.Y [Deliverable title]-vA.BB
where	A: Major version of the report
	BB: Minor version of the report for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	DIAMOND 1st Periodic Technical Report-v0.10
	DIAMOND 1st Periodic Financial Report-v0.10
	DIAMOND Final Technical Report-v0.10

Table 7 shows the naming conventions for internal documents, such as mailing lists and internal effort reporting, which are regularly updated.

Table 7. Naming conventions for internal documents which are regularly updated

Name	DIAMOND [Document description]_ddmmyy or DIAMOND [Document description] [Partner name]_ddmmyy
where	dd: date; mm: month; yy: year
	DIAMOND Mailing List_201022
Examples	DIAMOND Effort and Cost Reporting ICCS_201022

Finally, Table 8 presents the naming conventions for materials/publications of the project.

Table 8. Naming convention for DIAMOND materials/publications

Name	DIAMOND [Material/Publication]-vA.BB or DIAMOND [Material/Publication] [Short title]-vA.BB
where	A: Major version of the material/publication
	BB: Minor version of the material/publication for updates during the preparation phase
Examples	DIAMOND Policy Brief Issue 1: Stakeholder Inclusion in Modelling-v0.10
Notes	DIAMOND Newsletter No1-v0.10

2.4.2 Document management system

SharePoint is a web-based collaborative platform that integrates natively with Microsoft Office. SharePoint allows for storage, retrieval, searching, archiving, tracking, management, and reporting on electronic documents and records. SharePoint's integration with Microsoft Windows and Microsoft Office allows for collaborative real-time

editing and encrypted/information rights managed synchronisation. SharePoint team DIAMOND site includes a “Documents” library, which will host all documents related to the WP deliverables, the scientific content, and the administrative documents that should be shared among the consortium partners.

The documents are classified as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The DIAMOND internal data management platform

The structure is simple, yet comprehensive, allowing the user to identify/locate easily all documents related to the project. SharePoint offers various functionalities that secure proper document management, as reflected in Table 9.

Table 9. SharePoint functionalities securing proper document management.

Functionality	Description
Secure sharing of a document	To share a document uploaded onto the library, SharePoint creates a link that the user (creator of the document) can copy and send it to select recipient(s). For someone to access the document, they need to be a registered DIAMOND SharePoint user.
Replacing an existing document / Version history	SharePoint offers the user the capacity to upload new versions of an existing document. Versioning creates a historical record of all changes, with the date/time and indication of the user that made the change, on a per-file/list item basis. The end user can view, delete, and restore a version if they have the correct permissions in the library or list. Version History opens in a modal dialog box, with options to View, Restore, or Delete the entry. If any SharePoint Metadata columns were changed, that column and its new value will be displayed.
Locking a document	SharePoint offers the user the capacity to lock (check out) a document while they are editing it. Checking out a document stops other users from modifying it in any way, until the editing process is over.
Adding News	SharePoint allows users to create posts like announcements, people news, status updates, and more that can include graphics and rich formatting.
Creating a List	SharePoint offer user the capacity to create and share lists to track issues, tasks, and more. Start from a template, Excel file, or from scratch.

Overall, SharePoint provides a central point, where DIAMOND partners can access project documents and collaborate on their development. Advantages of the system include:

- Documents in a single place. DIAMOND partners know that all project documents can be found on

SharePoint.

- Document tracking. SharePoint allows the development of a document to be tracked: document versions are numbered, collaboration is structured, and old versions of documents are stored rather than overwritten.
- Ownership recorded. When a document is uploaded onto SharePoint, information regarding the date, time and author is all recorded.
- Risk reduction. Using SharePoint reduces reliance on WP and task leaders to manage document collaboration via other routes, such as email, Dropbox, etc. SharePoint also allows document changes to be 'rolled back', reducing the risk of work being lost due to files being accidentally overwritten or deleted.
- Document availability. SharePoint is a web-based system that is accessible via computers, smartphones and tablets. One can access documents wherever they are.

The management team from ICCS will be responsible for securing that SharePoint, and no other tool, is used for document management. In particular, the PC will ensure that:

- all documents related to the work carried out in DIAMOND are uploaded onto SharePoint;
- all partners use SharePoint to collaborate on documents produced with DIAMOND partners, rather than other tools, such as e-mail, Dropbox, or Google Drive;
- all consortium partners have access to all relevant documents; and
- document collaboration is not delayed by consortium partners, in particular WPLs, being on missions, on holidays or working on other assignments outside DIAMOND.

2.5 Internal communication

Effective channels, processes, and tasks for internal communication have already been established since Month 1, in order to facilitate effective coordination, knowledge sharing, smooth cooperation and direct communication of the implementation and dissemination of information for partners.

2.5.1 Physical meetings

The kick-off meeting (M1) and the 2nd GA meeting took place in Athens and Bilbao, respectively, as hybrid events. Regular project meetings will be held on a six-month basis to ensure that all procedures are understood and implemented as planned. For sustainability reasons, these will be back-to-back with other physical events organised by the project or held online. The management team from ICCS is responsible for the organisation of the agenda of the meetings. In case of an emergency or in need of a conflict resolution, ad-hoc meetings may be organised upon decision of the GA. A tentative schedule of project meetings is available in Table 10.

Table 10. Tentative schedule of DIAMOND physical (GA) meetings.

Meeting identifier	Time	Place
Kick-off Meeting	December 2022 (M1)	Athens
2nd GA Meeting	May 2023 (M6)	Bilbao
3rd GA Meeting	November 2023 (M12)	TBD
4th GA Meeting	May 2024 (M18)	TBD
5th GA Meeting	November 2024 (M24)	TBD
6th GA Meeting	May 2025 (M30)	TBD
7th GA Meeting	November 2025 (M36)	TBD
8th GA Meeting	May 2026 (M42)	TBD
Final Event	November 2026 (M48)	TBD

Proposed dates for each meeting will be discussed in online meetings and decided over doodle polls organised by the management team from ICCS, at an early stage—i.e., at least four (4) months before a physical meeting.

2.5.2 Remote meetings

Remote meetings (through Microsoft Teams) will be employed for the effective communication among project partners during the project lifecycle. Monthly **EB meetings** will ensure that the project is on track towards achieving its objectives and vision as well as provide WP updates (with reviews and appropriate revisions of the work) to enable following a realistic time schedule and introducing corrective actions in a timely fashion. The management team from ICCS is responsible for the organisation of the agenda and for the coordination of these meetings. The meetings' details (day, time, Microsoft Teams link, agenda) will be communicated by the management team from ICCS at least 1 week before the date of each meeting, to allow time to the participants for scheduling and preparing all necessary information for each meeting. Remote and hybrid meetings will be recorded, after consent from all participants is granted. The minutes of each project meeting (physical, hybrid, and remote) will be drafted right after each meeting. The minutes will be compiled into one document forming part of deliverable D1.2, 'Report on Project and SAB Meetings', due in Month 12 and with updates in Months 30 (D1.3) and 48 (D1.4).

In addition, remote WP meetings will be held on an ad-hoc basis, initiated by the respective WPL, in coordination with the PC, who will be present in these meetings. WP meetings will also serve for conflict resolution.

Generally, technical issues or conflicts within the contractual commitments that do not involve any contract, budget, resource allocation or overall project focus changes will be discussed at WP level first. If the decisions reached at WP level are unacceptable by any single consortium partner, the conflict will be resolved according to a conflict resolution procedure that can be summarised in the next steps:

1. The consortium members involved in the implementation of the WP inform the WPL for the emerging conflict.
2. The WPL decides whether the issue needs to be discussed in a bilateral teleconference or a dedicated WP meeting. The WPL then informs the PC for the planned actions.
3. The result of the bilateral teleconference or the meeting is communicated to the PC.
4. If no consensus has been reached thus far, the PC contacts the responsible persons and tries to resolve the conflict.
5. If the disagreement remains, the issue is escalated to the EB. The decision that will be made at that level will be considered as the final resolution of the issue.

Minutes of WP meetings will be drafted by the WPL following the template, to be shared with the consortium.

2.5.3 Weekly updates

The PC will be sending weekly updates (e.g., every Friday) in the form of an e-mail to inform DIAMOND partners about the latest updates regarding the implementation of the project. The update will include *inter alia* reminders about upcoming deliverables and project meetings, information about international events and involvement of the consortium, useful documentation and produced material and deliverables, requests for action by partners, etc. Thus, all partners can always have an updated overview of the project implementation and progress, effectively communicated.

2.6 Internal reporting

For internal project management and monitoring purposes, partners will be submitting every 18 months their actual use of human resources to the PC, for the purposes of preparing the interim (midterm and final) reports—unless otherwise necessitated by the Commission. This includes sub-contracting, travel, and other direct costs spent in the framework of the project for each of the reporting periods (Month 1 to 18, Month 19 to 36, and Month 37 to M48, see below).

As far as internal reporting of human effort and other costs is concerned, a dedicated template has been created and will be used by all beneficiaries.

Finally, as per Article 20.1 of the Grant Agreement, the consortium partners will be keeping time records for the number of hours declared. These records will be in writing and approved by the persons working on the action and their supervisors, at least monthly.

Each partner will be responsible for keeping their time records, but there will be no obligation to submit them to the PC.

2.7 Official reporting

According to Article 21.2 of the Grant Agreement, the project is divided into the following ‘reporting periods’ (RPs):

- RP1: from Month 1 to Month 18 (i.e., December 2022 – May 2024)
- RP2: from Month 19 to Month 36 (i.e., June 2024 – November 2025)
- RP3: from Month 37 to Month 48 (i.e., December 2025 – November 2026)

Articles 21.3 and 21.4 of the Grant Agreement describe in detail the content of the periodic report covering RP1 and the final report covering RP2.

The periodic technical report shall consist of two parts:

- Part A, generated by the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal, which requires that the PC, on behalf of the consortium, answer to a questionnaire covering issues related to project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and the Horizon Europe monitoring requirements; and
- Part B, the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the partners during the reporting period.

The information will be regularly inserted into the template, in order to allow timely submission of the report, ensuring that all necessary information is provided to the EC. Part A will be also fed into on a regular basis.

The process to ensure high quality in the delivery of the official reports consists of the following steps (Table 11):

Table 11. Process for the delivery of the official progress reports

When	Who	What	Recipient
1 month before the end of the reporting period	PC	Asks the consortium partners to insert information in the periodic report template within three weeks	All consortium partners
1 week before the end of the reporting period	All consortium partners	Provide their technical inputs, filling in the template	PC
1 week after the end of the reporting period	All consortium partners	Provide their final resources consumption (submit their own financial statement on the Participant Portal)	EC
2 weeks after the end of the reporting period	PC	Synthesises and shares the draft periodic report (Parts A and B in Word templates) for internal review	QM, PM, EM
3 weeks after the end of the reporting period	QM	Provides feedback on the draft periodic report	PC

When	Who	What	Recipient
3 weeks after the end of the reporting period	PC	Shares PM's, EM's, PC's and QM's feedback/comments with partners and asks that concerns be addressed within one week.	All consortium partners
1 month after the end of the reporting period	All consortium partners	Provide their final inputs/ modifications, if any, in respect to comments raised affecting them, if any	PC
5 weeks after the end of the reporting period	PC	Puts together final report and submits to the EC	EC

The above time schedule provides the PC with three extra weeks to address, if necessary, any remaining issues before eventually submitting the report to the EC, as per Article 21 of the GA.

For associated partners (ETH, UNIBAS, EPFL, and Imperial, Oxford, UCL), this otherwise-template process will be done with respect to their internal processes and obligations towards their funding bodies (SERI and UKRI, respectively).

2.8 Quality Assurance of Deliverables

In this section, the necessary activities to assess, analyse, and improve the quality of project outputs are described.

2.8.1 Review roles and responsibilities

The following actors will be engaged in the process for the review of deliverables.

Quality Manager (QM): The QM, whose role can be framed like that of an Editor of a peer-reviewed scientific journal, will be supervising the quality assurance process, in close contact with the ICCS management team. For certain cases of critical deliverables (e.g., research works), the QM will review their quality and provide feedback during the 2nd round of the review process. The QM will have the authority to closely follow the progress in any deliverable on an ad hoc basis—including having the final say on a review comment, in the instance deliverable leader and reviewer disagree on the way forward.

Internal reviewers: They are responsible to thoroughly read the draft deliverable, assess its quality against pre-defined criteria (see Table 14) and provide clear comments for improvement. The internal reviewers will be involved in the first review round, following the original submission of the draft version of a deliverable. In case, during the second review round performed by the PM and the PC (see below), the quality of the deliverable is still not deemed to be in line with the standards set nor adequate for submission to the EC services, the two internal reviewers may be invited for one or more revision iterations, until the deliverable is ready for final submission to the EC services.

Deliverable Leaders: They prepare the backbone (table of contents) of the deliverable, allocate tasks to, and coordinate the work of, the contributors and are responsible to consolidate the inputs of all contributors into the draft deliverable to be submitted for review and publication. They must address the comments made by the internal reviewers to improve the quality of the deliverable.

Deliverable contributors: They are responsible to draft parts of the deliverable, as per the allocation of tasks performed by the Deliverable Leader, and to deliver their inputs in a timely way to the Deliverable Leader.

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC will be involved in the entire review process, either as one of the reviewers or in continuous communication with the PM (see below) and the team of reviewers.

Project Manager (PM): The PM will be involved in the entire review process, meaning that the PM must review both the draft version submitted for review by the respective Deliverable Leader and the revised version submitted after addressing the comments raised by the internal reviewers. The PM will be reviewing all deliverables.

Member of the management team from ICCS: One member of the management team from ICCS will oversee the final editing of the deliverable before the official submission to the Participant Portal. This is a final technical check that the deliverable complies with the template and that the deliverable is ready to be uploaded, ensuring that the text is free of spelling/grammar/syntactic/semantic errors, as well as of comments, and highlighted text. Other aspects (page numbering and table of contents, figures, tables, etc.) will be also checked.

2.8.2 Deliverable Review process

Each project deliverable will be quality-reviewed by 2-5 internal reviewers from the consortium (depending on the nature of the deliverable), by the PM, and an additional member of the management team from ICCS.

2.8.2.1 Assignment of reviewers

The PM invites, through the weekly update, all consortium partners to declare their interest in reviewing the upcoming deliverables for the next year (twelve months). Partners declare interest and the PM then allocates reviewers based on the respective partner's technical expertise and overall availability. The number of deliverables to be reviewed by each consortium partners depends on the background/expertise as well as is subject to the budget and effort share in the project (for allocation of reviewers for Year 1 deliverables, see Annex I).

2.8.2.2 Review steps

For each deliverable of the upcoming year, once the reviewers are assigned, the following steps take place to secure timely submission of the deliverable (Table 12).

Table 12. Deliverable Review process

(By) When	Initiator	What	Recipient
5 weeks before the official submission deadline	PM	verifies interest and informs of the review period/deadlines	The assigned internal reviewers
4 weeks before the official submission deadline	Deliverable Leader	submits the first draft deliverable to SharePoint and informs by e-mail the PM	PM
4 weeks before the official submission deadline	PM	informs of the submitted draft deliverable	The assigned internal reviewers
3 weeks before the official submission deadline	Assigned internal reviewers, PM	submit the reviewed deliverable with their comments (activating track changes in the Word document) to SharePoint and inform the PM by e-mail	PM
3 weeks before the official submission deadline	PM	informs the deliverable Leader and invites them to address the comments of the reviewers	The deliverable Leader

(By) When	Initiator	What	Recipient
10 days before the official submission deadline	Deliverable Leader	submits the revised (second draft) deliverable to SharePoint and informs the PM by e-mail	PM
5 days before the official submission deadline	PM	reviews the revised deliverable; and submit it to SharePoint for final editing	PM
2 days before the official submission deadline	Assigned member of the management team from NUTA	copyedits the deliverable and informs the PM	PM
2 days before the official submission deadline	PM	Submits the deliverable to the Participant's Portal	SyGMa
2 days before the official submission deadline	PM	Informs about the submission of the deliverable	All consortium partners

The quality of the deliverables will be assessed against specific quality criteria to ensure uniformity and consistency in the review process of all deliverables and to ensure the reviewers' clear understanding of and compliance with the process. The criteria, along with the aspects to be investigated, are outlined in Table 13.

Table 13. Quality criteria for deliverables

Quality Criteria	Description
Clarity	The language of the text is clear (proper sentence structure is used); The text is in English (UK); The text is unambiguous; The terminology, including acronyms, is explained; There are no spelling errors; Any potentially sensitive information is appropriately worded
Completeness	All aspects of the deliverable, as described in Annex I (Part A) of the GA, are comprehensively addressed
Accuracy	All factual information used in the deliverable is supported by the respective references
Added value	Each aspect of the deliverable is analysed in adequate detail; The deliverable has scientific and/or policy value, as envisaged by the project; The language of the text is useful to the targeted audience (e.g. scientists, policymakers, etc.)
Relevance	The content is relevant to the scope of the deliverable; The deliverable is relevant to the targeted readers/audience
Compliance	The text is written in line with the deliverable template
Originality	The text does not violate academic integrity and avoids plagiarism. It includes appropriate attributions and citations when paraphrasing and summarising the work of others. Generative artificial intelligence (AI) and AI-assisted technologies should only be used to improve readability and language, with human oversight. Deliverable authors should disclose the use of such technologies and acknowledge full responsibility. In case reviewers identify violations of the aforementioned guidelines, deliverables will be extensively screened using established tools (e.g., Turnitin, tools for detecting AI-generated text etc.).

Quality Criteria	Description
Conciseness	The text is clear and does not include vague words or language. It avoids repetition, tautology, and unnecessary words.

Clear instructions will be given to all reviewers by the PC and the QM so that they assess the deliverables against all the above-mentioned criteria when they perform the review.

2.9 Quality Assurance of other material

The other scientific and policy-related outputs of the project—i.e., the project commentaries, policy briefs, and working documents—will also be reviewed before they are published, mainly for compliance with the respective templates. As there are no deadlines and no formal submission for these materials, the process only includes one step, delivery of the draft document by the dissemination leader, based on the inputs of the authors, and a technical check by the management team from ICCS (as a bare minimum).

Templates are also developed for other, communication-related, project material (e.g., newsletters and press releases). For this type of resource, the management team from ICCS will be reviewing the content of every produced resource for completeness and scientific relevance, its compliance with the obligations set out in the Description of the Action, and its format for compliance with the respective template.

3 Quality assessment

3.1 Evaluation framework

The consortium has defined two levels of self-evaluation of the DIAMOND project.

The first one is related to the assessment against the performance indicators set under the expected policy, societal, and research/scientific impacts reflected in Annex I (Part B) of the Grant Agreement. The second one is associated with the internal processes and the quality of operations of the project. The performance indicators are meant to measure the performance of the consortium against the principles and processes presented in the current QMP.

The team responsible for the quality assessment tasks, such as the data collection, data analysis and synthesis and reporting, is the project management team from ICCS, supervised by the PC and coordinated by the PM. ICCS will be collecting data regularly, closely working with all partners, and will be updating the values of the indicators on a six-month basis, which will allow the consortium to take corrective measures if needed, in a timely manner.

3.2 Performance indicators

The tables in Annex II and Annex III summarise a) the indicators per outcome and impact and b) the communication and dissemination indicators respectively. For each indicator, the target values are extracted from Annex I (Part A) of the Grant Agreement and the column for the current value will be updated on a six-month basis (the current value at the beginning of the project is zero).

Annex IV refers to the indicators for the assessment of the quality of operations and processes of implementation.

4 Risk management plan

The Risk Management Plan consists of the identification of the technical (research-oriented) and management (project implementation-related) risks; the assessment of their degree of occurrence, and of their potential impact; and of reducing the possibility of materialisation for each one of the risks already foreseen in the design of the project by planning the necessary mitigation measures to be taken during implementation.

4.1 Risk analysis and mitigation measures

The risk probability and impact are reflected in the following linguistic values (Table 14).

Table 14. Linguistic values for risk impact and risk probability occurrence

Level of likelihood	Level of severity
Low	Low
Medium	Medium
High	High

Table 15 presents the risks that have been identified already since the proposal phase and the proposed mitigation measures.

Table 15. Identified risks and mitigation measures

Risk ID	Description of Risk	WPs Involved	Risk Likelihood	Risk Severity	Proposed Risk Mitigation Measures
1	Partner(s) unable to contribute	All	Low	High	Rigorous project management. Failure of individual participants will lead to immediate assessment of capabilities and task reassignment. Partners have adequate range of technical skills and can take over tasks.
2	Partners' contribution to outputs are not delivered on time	All	Medium	Low	Quality management, early directions for timely outputs. Monthly calls on WPs (reviews/appropriate revisions) for corrective actions. 7 of 50 deliverables in first year indicating issues; 10 milestones to track progress.
3	Low scientific and technical quality of deliverables	All	Low	High	Rigorous quality management. First deliverable drafts one month prior to deadline, for thorough internal review, detailed feedback by Coordinator, 2-5 reviewers. Partners have excellent track record for scientific quality.
4	Low engagement of stakeholders	WP2	Medium	Medium	Partners will mobilise their existing networks & experience in co-creation and maintenance of CDE nodes. SAB will be asked to support if needed.
5	Lack of coordination with other actors, wrong expectations	All	Low	Medium	Acknowledging the requirement of inclusiveness in the climate dialogue, project is oriented to co-creation (WP2). Partners' expertise in and access to transdisciplinary toolboxes to be used in corrective settings, if needed
6	Limited policy impact due to COVID-19 and delays to major policy or scientific processes	WP5, WP4, WP7, WP3	Low	Medium	Project planning fits well in policy schedule. If COP sessions, the Global Stocktake, or IPCC/other processes are affected, impact is still envisaged beyond project duration. Disruptions will be seen as 'research opportunity' to develop models with capacity to analyse extreme events
7	Limited participation of external experts	WP6, WP2	Medium	Low	Robust and rigorous CDE plan (Task 6.2) dynamically updated promoting project with all possible means. To maximise participation, we will use existing knowhow in establishing an effective communication platform.

Risk ID	Description of Risk	WPs Involved	Risk Likelihood	Risk Severity	Proposed Risk Mitigation Measures
8	Difficulty in organising and attending stakeholder interactions:	WP2	Medium	Medium	Organisation responsibility for physical stakeholder interactions centrally by 2 partners. #staygrounded: some workshops online, acknowledging COVID-19 implications may hinder traveling of partners/stakeholders
9	Limited transparency of the modelling processes	WP5, WP4, WP6, WP2, WP3	Low	High	The project emphasises openness and new business/research models for IAMs transparency (entire WP6). Open protocols for modelling, scenario building, and model development early & regularly updated. Stakeholders to drive model co-development and use. All new models/modules will be released in open access, with training kits. All datasets in open repository.
10	Vulnerability of modelling to different types of uncertainty	WP5, WP4, WP3,	Low	Medium	Robustness of modelling outcomes is a core aim of DIAMOND, as it orients to a diverse model ensemble. Two models specifically designed for stochastic uncertainty (GCAM, PROMETHEUS). Further enhancing robustness against uncertainties constitutes one of core tasks (Task 5.2).
11	Limited legitimacy of models, methods, and tools	WP6, WP2, WP3	Low	High	Technical/policy briefs on capacity of new models produced, effectively disseminated. Model development (in WP3), integration (in WP4) and use (in WP5) driven by stakeholders (in WP2) and based on their needs. Open software development practice to be strictly followed/corrected (in WP6).
12	Limited contribution to major international scientific assessments (e.g., IPCC reports)	All	Low	Medium	Partners participate in networks supporting assessments (IAMC, EMF, etc.). Several members were IPCC AR6 authors; all six IAMs directly contributed to IPCC AR6. Steering efforts to supporting climate dialogue, SAB features personalities with remarkable track record in IPCC reports.
13	Data not being forthcoming from various sources	WP5, WP4, WP6, WP3	Medium	Low	Existing open datasets to be used for new IAM developments (WP3) and use (WP5)—in detail in Section 1.2.2. Sector-relevant datasets will be made openly available via soft/hard links with WP4 models. If datasets (e.g., IEA's) are not made open, alternative open datasets to be prioritised.

ANNEX I: Allocation of reviewers to deliverables (Year 1)

Work Package	Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Due Date	Deliverable Leader	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3	Reviewer 4	Reviewer 5
3	1	Model development strategy	3-Mar-2023	BC3	Imperial	HOLISTIC	ICCS	CYI	-
6	1	Open data management plan	3-Mar-2023	ICCS	Imperial	BC3	-	-	-
7	1	DIAMOND visual identity & website	3-Mar-2023	HOLISTIC	ICCS	ISINNOVA	-	-	-
2	1	Multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy	31-Mar-2023	ISINNOVA	ICCS	UNIBAS	-	-	-
1	1	Quality management plan	3-May-2023	ICCS	CICERO	UCL	-	-	-
7	2	The DIAMOND Project CDE Plan	3-May-2023	HOLISTIC	ICCS	ETH	-	-	-
1	2	Report on project and SAB Meetings	2-Nov-2023	ICCS	ICCS (Internal)	-	-	-	-

ANNEX II: Outcome & Impact Indicators

Expected Outcomes (EO) / Expected Impacts (EI)	Performance Indicator / Targets
<p>EO1</p> <p>Improved adequacy of Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) to effectively contribute to international, European, national, and regional climate policy processes in support of the implementation of the European Green Deal, the Paris Agreement, COVID-19 recovery and broader sustainability goals</p>	<p>(i) improved and open-source versions of six leading IAMs with high sectoral and technological detail, spatial and temporal resolution, and EU level granularity (MS8), as well as enhanced capacity in representing physical impacts, extreme events (such as pandemics), political feasibility, societal desirability, finance markets, and interactions with the broader agenda for sustainable development (D3.4-D3.9); (ii) one report on enhanced household heterogeneity representation in at least 3 IAMs (D4.3); (iii) one new module for at least 3 IAMs (MS10), and one report, on enhanced representation of behavioural change (D4.6); (iv) one report on better representation of finance and labour dynamics, including a novel operationalisation of well-being in IAMs (D4.5); (v) one interoperable, opensource electricity module for at least 3 IAMs (D4.7) (vi) over 10 scientific publications on IAM improvements.</p>
<p>EO2</p> <p>Contributions to major international scientific assessments such as the reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) and the International Resource Panel (IRP).</p>	<p>(i) one statistical model relating economic, technological, and governance parameters to emissions pathways and two reports on scenario classes missing from IPCC scenario databases to date (D5.1-D5.2); (ii) a novel risk assessment framework and a report quantifying impacts of common systematic biases in current modelling, providing guidance on future development priorities and IPCC assessments (D5.7); (iii) at least two papers on role of infilling and harmonisation in scenario output diversity and missing human-physical couplings in CMIP-type experiments; (iv) at least 30 references to project outputs in upcoming IPCC, IPBES, IRP reports; (v) project acknowledgement in at least 5 IPCC AR7 chapters and/or upcoming special reports; (vi) enhancements to 6 leading IAMs used in key international scientific assessments; (vii) project referenced in future UNEP's Emissions Gap reports.</p>
<p>EO3</p> <p>Increased robustness, legitimacy, relevance, usability, and transparency of IAMs leading to increased uptake and better awareness of their results across various end-user groups, developing, where possible, new business models for IAMs transparency (for example, open source and open code options)</p>	<p>(i) three reports on open data management for IAM advancements (D6.1-D6.3); (ii) a broad, vibrant, active community of practice, with 2 reports on planning for and lessons learnt in the process (D6.4-D6.5); (iii) one report on open-source development pipelines (D6.6); (iv) one report on novel open science protocols and diagnostics for IAM development (D6.7); (v) an IAM Application Library in I2AM PARIS (D6.8-D6.9), with at least 20 applications of IAM results; (vi) two reports on orchestrating (MS4) and implementing innovative synergies with research projects (D6.10); (vii) I2AM PARIS expanded by 6 new IAMs, co-created and used by at least 80 stakeholders and 100 modellers; (viii) 20 presentations on SlideShare and at least 20 open-access papers on methodological advancements (Zenodo); (ix) contribution to 3 openmod workshops; (x) overall interdisciplinary guidance of IAM developments via a diverse scientific advisory board (MS1); (xi) 1 business guide on exploiting IAM results in practical action.</p>

EO4	<p>Enhanced coherence between climate action (mitigation, understanding of impacts, climate risks and adaptation) and other environmental/sustainability objectives, notably biodiversity, based on a more realistic representation of their interactions, including co-benefits and trade-offs</p>	<p>(i) expanded version of the ENGAGE circularity model to cover 2 more industrial sectors (MS7) and one report on expanded capacity of 3 IAMs for circularity performance (D4.1); (ii) expanded version of the MAGPIE global land-use model (MS7), one report on the expanded capacity of 2 IAMs to capture the potential and limitations of nature-based solutions for climate action (D4.2); (iii) expansion of 4 IAMs to capture land-use and climate-carbon feedback uncertainty for policy-relevant scenarios defined by warming risk thresholds(D4.4); (iv) a series of dynamic infographics in I2AM PARIS mapping all 6 advanced IAMs to their capacity to extract SDG indicators (MS9); (v)one policy report on synergies and trade-offs of broader climate action with other SDGs (D5.6); (vi) one policy report on the interplay of mitigation with adaptation, with a focus on agriculture, land-use change, and biodiversity (D5.3); (vii) at least 5 papers and 1 policy brief on synergies among mitigation, adaptation, and broader sustainability targets</p>
EO5	<p>More active involvement of citizens in climate action based on better understanding and demonstration of how small-scale actions contribute to the achievement of large-scale climate policy objectives including through socially innovative approaches, and better understanding of which actions/policies are more effective</p>	<p>(i) three reports on how different stakeholders, including policymakers, industry decision-makers, and citizens, can be better engaged in climate science and policy (D2.1-D2.3); (ii) two policy reports on stakeholder-informed research questions (D2.4.-D2.5); (iii) at least four ethical and strategic foresight workshops with citizens and other climate stakeholders (MS6) and one report on synthesis of co-produced knowledge (D2.6); (iv) one report on how to promote model co-ownership, quality, societal robustness, and practical relevance (D2.7); (v) four reports on stakeholder-driven specifications for IAM co-development (D3.1-D3.3, MS5); (vi) one policy brief on the quantified contributions of citizen actions to mitigation policy targets; (vii) anonymised decision datasets from cross-national surveys (D4.6).</p>
EO6	<p>Ultimately, accelerated transition towards climate neutrality based on improved knowledge and better designed policies that are more integrated, greener, healthier, more inclusive.</p>	<p>(i) one collection of policy reports on user-driven scenarios of increasingly ambitious climate action, based on the enhanced modelling capabilities of the project’s 6 IAMs, in individual model inter-comparison projects that explore the role of realistic behavioural change, distributional impacts, and the dynamic interplay of climate action with finance and labour dynamics, as well as alternative growth paradigms and well-being therein, integrated mitigation and adaptation actions, co-benefits on health, employment, and biodiversity (D5.5); (ii) a policy report on resilient mitigation pathways to net-zero against extraordinary extremes (extreme events and geopolitical challenges) (D5.4); (iii) 6 new workspaces in I2AM PARIS on long-term mitigation pathways and advice for the EU and Member States as well as global action; (iv) over 10 papers on national, regional, and global pathways, considering physical impacts, disruptive changes, societal innovations, COVID-19, and SDGs; (v) at least 4 policy briefs for EU & national action; (vi) 1 business guide on detailed financial flows and reskilling needs of the transition in the EU and globally.</p>

E11	Advancing knowledge and providing solutions in earth system science; pathways to climate neutrality; social science for climate action; and better understanding of climate-ecosystems interactions	(i) impact on the targets of the EU Strategic Plan's Key Strategic Orientation C for making Europe the first circular, climate-neutral, sustainable economy; (ii) evidence cited by the EC in its climate goals; (iii) 6 well-established IAMs with highly advanced capabilities to help drive climate science and authoritatively underpin policy
E12	Contributing substantially to key international assessments such as those of the IPCC or the EEA	(i) at least 60 references to outputs of the 6 new IAMs in this decade's IPCC, IPBES, IRP reports; (ii) better collaboration among the three IPCC Working Groups; (iii) over 30 scenario submissions to IPCC AR7
E13	Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA) on climate change	(i) contribution to establishing I2AM PARIS as a vessel of the modelling community (at least 5 Horizon projects supporting it); (ii) over 70 IAMs (& 10 non-project workspaces) in I2AM PARIS; (iii) new modules exploited by at least 10 IAM teams after project end; (iv) Over 10 papers, and at least 5 events held, jointly with other projects
E14	Increasing the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate change for use by policy makers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens	(i) use of the enhanced models in at least 5 national climate action plans among Member States and outside Europe; (ii) acknowledgement of the project in development of national plans for climate in at least 5 countries; (iii) uptake of DIAMOND results by at least five industries from emissions-heavy sectors; (iv) at least 30 new scenarios added and explained in the I2AM PARIS platform; (v) harmonisation & model integration/evaluation protocols established in modelling society; (vi) at least 10 non-academic articles related to project outcomes in media

ANNEX III: Communication and Dissemination activities and indicators

Task	Dissemination and exploitation objectives	Main dissemination channel/activity	Months
T2.1	Create a protocol and a communication strategy to govern stakeholder engagement	Dialogue-driven protocol shared through the platform and direct consultation with all stakeholder groups	5,17, 19
T2.2	Frame current gaps in IAMs and define research questions with stakeholders (IAM community, policymakers, industry & NGOs)	Multilateral (workshops, e-meetings, webinars, surveys) and bilateral (interviews, phone calls) communication with each stakeholder group.	7-30
T2.3	Co-create DIAMOND's IAM improvements and scenario exercises with stakeholders	As in T2.2, plus synthesis of policy, industrial, societal perspectives for robust and relevant models/pathways	19-36
T2.4	Promote co-ownership of new models with the stakeholders	Jointly assess quality of new models using workshops and methods off the td-net transdisciplinarity toolbox	31-47
T6.1	Establish and sustain communities of practice for integrated assessment modelling to other modelling teams and disciplines	Establish synergies with relevant projects/consortia, interdisciplinary interactions, capacity development, encourage participation in open-source development	1-48
T6.2, T6.3	Share tools and strategies for advanced software development in IAMs as well as improved model diagnostics and protocols	Disseminate the tools to IAM community via project workshops, external conferences (e.g., IAMC, IEW, EMP-E), and the I2 AM PARIS platform	1-48
T6.4, T6.5	Expand I2AM PARIS and establish it as a vessel of the EU modelling community	Enhanced I2 AM PARIS platform (new workspaces, application library); open science practices, FAIR data	1-48
T7.3	Boost scientific and policy outreach of project methods and results, as well as societal impact	Scientific articles, special issues, consortia meetings, conferences, policy briefs, infographics, videos	1-48

Activity	Objective	Expected audience	Monitoring tool
DIAMOND visual identity (Task 7.1)	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project to all stakeholder groups	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> policy industry, research, civil society	Summary of all monitoring means
Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform (Task 6.2 & 6.1-6.5)	Facilitating data harmonisation and modelling. Fostering co-creation of assumptions, parameters, scenarios	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> 2,000 unique users/year 40% of return visitors	Google Analytics

Project website (Task 7.1)	Aiming to present and disseminate results and be a referenced source with useful modelling material and links	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> 2,000 unique visitors/year 40% of return visitors	Google Analytics account set up when website launched.
Networking activities with EU projects under same or relevant topics (Tasks 6.1)	Creating awareness of the project and sharing results among the energy research, social science, and climate-economy modelling communities	<u>Academia</u> Project reference in 20 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	Digital monitoring, number of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers
Social Media channels (Task 7.2)	Creating awareness of objectives, scope, results among science, policy, industry, citizens, and other groups	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> 1,000 uses of #climatediamond 500 followers on LinkedIn	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn analytics, Twitonomy
Commentaries, briefs, bi-monthly newsletters (Task 7.3)	Creating awareness and involving stakeholders in progress; reports and commentaries of policy interest	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> 4,000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics
Infographics and Videos (Task 7.3)	Creating awareness and familiarity with project objectives and results (especially among non-experts)	<u>Civil society, policymakers</u> > 1500 views (videos) 400 downloads (infographics)	YouTube/Instagram statistics; number of downloads
Blog posts, press releases, articles in news sites (Task 7.3)	Articles on climate action, energy strategies, and sustainable lifestyles in leading news/media websites/blogs	<u>Civil society</u> At least 10 articles and press releases in the project's lifetime	Media monitoring Copies of articles shared on website
Policy briefs, business guides (Task 7.3)	Briefs and guides to inform policy and decision makers on climate action	<u>Policymakers, industry</u> 6 briefs and 2 business guides	Number of briefs/ guides
A final EU Conference (Task 7.2)	Sharing the final project results	<u>All stakeholder groups</u> Audience of 70-100	Number of attendees; minutes; photos
Scientific Outreach (Task 7.3)	Academic dissemination of the project's results (open access)	<u>Academia</u> > 50 papers; > 20 conferences	Digital monitoring

ANNEX IV: Quality indicators

Performance Indicator	Targets
% of comments of reviewers addressed by the Deliverable Leaders/authors	>90%
Average Delay (in days) in the submission of draft deliverables for internal review	<7
Average Delay (in days) in the submission of the final deliverables to the Participants Portal	0
Average number of inconsistencies according to the deliverable template (format, layout, spelling, etc.) in the versions ready for the final editing before submission	<3
% of internal effort reports delivered on time	>80%
Delay (in days) in the submission of the periodic report	0
Delay (in days) in the submission of the final report	0